

Impact of Citizenship Amendment Act 2019 on Tribal Rights and Autonomy in Tripura

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The consistent demand for autonomous tribal state in Tripura is rooted in the long history of accommodating and transforming large tribal area with Bengali speaking plainsmen and eventual uprooting of tribal dwellers towards the forests. Although effective decentralization combined with successful land reforms and systematic promotion of agriculture has contributed to a large extent in the overall development of the state, the tribal rights remain a significant problem in the region. The tribals in the region continue to struggle for getting access of their own agricultural lands, forests, etc. and they are being deprived of education, health and livelihood. The situation stiffens further with the New Citizenship Amendment Bill 2019 as it leads to growing wave of resentment among the state's tribal population. The paper looks at the root causes of such contentions as well as implications of the CAB in the region.

Keywords: Citizenship Amendment Act 2019, History of Tripura, Tribal Rights, Autonomy in Tripura

Introduction

'Brata Kumar Reang'-- a farmer from Gachhimpara village of Dashda block in the ex-tremist dominated Dhalai district of North Tripura has had to barter his son in exchange for just 10 kg of rice. Unable to feed his family, Reang first sold his cattle and when the situation got worse, he sold his four-year-old son to his neighbour, who was a little better off than him. ".though incidents like the Gachhimpara case are rare, they are not unheard of," echoed in the words of Partho Deb of Dainik Sambad—one of Tripura's leading newspaper.¹ Glimpses of deaths from malnutrition usually are very common in this area. In the words Anu Mukherji, president of Tripura Adibashi Mahila Samity (NGO), "lack of rains is not the only reason for the food crisis in Tripura. It is the restriction on jhum cultivation".² Many such narratives shape the reality of Tribal population in Tripura today.

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Diverse issues pertaining to the relentless turmoil in daily life; relative deprivation and discrimination across spheres; lack of substantive opportunities in education as well as low representation in political decision-making; and the overall bottlenecks in the development process in the region --all together drive the discourse of Tribal Rights in Tripura. There has been strong voices over the decade for creating a separate state called 'Tipraland' by the Indigenous People's Front of Tripura (IPFT), which although is allied with the present BJP government in the state, still keeping their foot on the ground for getting their justice. While promises of considering the demands for a separate state were given by the current BJP government before forming the government, however, it has altered such promises and is settling down the issue with 'creating a modality committee' to look after the overall development of Tribal in the state. More so, with the state council overpowering the Autonomous District Council as the functional authority for this modality committee and the relative powerlessness of Autonomous District Council has led to a political rift between IPFT and BJP in the state at present. As the Citizenship Amendment Bill 2019 has been enacted recently, it intensifies the ongoing crisis of Tribal Rights and their autonomy in the region. The Bill has been perceived as threat to the existence of indigenous people in the region and is being strongly opposed by Tripura Tribal parties. Joint Movement against Citizenship Amendment Bill (JMCAB) has declared an indefinite Tripura bandh from December 9, 2019 in protest against the Citizenship Amendment Bill 2019 (7th Dec, 2019, NE NOW News, Agartala).³

Conceptualizing Tribal Rights and Issues in India

For a long time, the discourse around Tribal rights and their autonomy in India has arrested the attention of political thinkers, sociologists, civil rights activists—who share diverse opinions on defining the community, their distinct socio-cultural set up, the unique features and ethnic origin have substantially argued for either keeping them isolated or integrated into the mainstream land. While sociologist like M.S Ghurye advocated against any special status to be given to the community, sociologists like Verrier Elwin strongly voiced out for an integrationist approach unlike Ghurye (Stuligross, 1999).⁴ Elwin refuted the idea of an isolationist perspective (put forth by Ghurye) of tribal population and advocated for their continuous connection with rest of India as he expressed that a policy of "museumification" would stifle further tribal development (Stuligross, 1999). He holds that, integration of tribal population as a community into mainstream India would benefit both and fuel their mutual development. Thus, he emphasised on the idea of "tribal distinctiveness" and advocated for provisions of some political and social autonomy for tribal communities in independent India.

Statistically, the tribal population of the country, as per 2011 census, stands 10.43 crore, constituting 8.6% of the total population (Indian Government Census, 2011). Out of total population, 89.97% of them live in rural areas and 10.03% in urban areas (ibid). Broadly, the Scheduled Tribes⁵ reside in two distinct geographical area – the Central India and the North- Eastern Area. While more than half of the Scheduled Tribe population is concentrated in Central India, i.e., Madhya Pradesh (14.7),

Chhattisgarh (7.5%), Jharkhand (8.3%), Andhra Pradesh (2.5%), Maharashtra (10.1%), Orissa (9.2%), Gujarat (8.5%) and Rajasthan (8.8%), in the overall northeastern states of Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Mizoram, and Nagaland, around 90 percent of the population is tribal (Census of India, 2011).⁶ The remaining northeast states of Assam, Manipur, Sikkim, and Tripura, tribal people constitute between 20 to 30 percent of the population. A total of 705 tribal communities (Chandramouli, 2013),⁷ have been identified within Indian territory and as per official information, of these North East states viz. Meghalaya, Mizoram, Manipur, Tripura, Sikkim, Assam, Nagaland and Arunachal Pradesh shelters approximately 130 major tribal communities.

Fig 1: Distribution of Tribal Population in India (image courtesy: www.vikaspedia.in)

In India, tribal people are usually called *adivasi*—an umbrella term for a heterogeneous set of ethnic and tribal groups who are considered the aboriginal population of India. While similar terms such as *atavika*, *vanavasi* ("forest dwellers"), or *girijan* ("hill people") are also used for the tribes of India, *adivasi* carries the specific meaning of being the original and autochthonous inhabitants of a given region and was specifically coined for that purpose in the 1930s.⁸ However, the term Adivasi is not as acceptable to the eastern and north-eastern tribal population. They prefer to be addressed by their names. Since, the claimants of being aboriginal are not limited to tribals in India, therefore, Adivasi and tribals must not be considered equivalent terms. Moreover, in the northeast the term *Adivasi* is mostly used for migrant tribal labourers and small peasants. The tribal people are known for their distinct culture, language, social and cultural organization, their close proximity with nature, and isolation from mainstream settlements and for the status of being economically underdeveloped. This economic underdevelopment and the process of their marginalisation can be traced back to the intrusion of British colonialism—responsible for appropriating resources and forest lands which were home to tribals. Jen Mog and Debbarma observed that “exploitation of forest-lands by both the British and then zamindars resulted in the clearing of huge tracts for commercial crops such as tea, coffee and rubber and allowing contractors to fell trees in the very heart of the forest. These actions deprived the tribal people of their livelihoods because many of them were hunters and gatherers of forest produce” (Mog and Debbarma 2018).

Subsequently, in the post-Independence period, tribal rights and their autonomy was pro-ected by the Constitution of India and ‘special status’ was provided to tribal areas by initiating the 5th and 6th schedule in the constitution. However, although tribal rights have been strengthened after independence by entitling them with reservation in the legislature, educational institutions and government jobs, the ground reality still betrays their constitutional rights. Majority of them reside in underserved forest regions with scarcity of basic civic amenities such as road, markets, transport, health care, safe drinking water or sanitation etc. Besides the so-called ‘development activities’ like construction of industries, roads, large dams, sale of timber, deforestation etc, —that have displaced tribal population from their forest land and marginalised the community, a huge influx of non-tribals in the ‘tribal belt’⁹ have further pushed them to the periphery. The issues and rights pertaining to the tribal community has been a persistent concern in India. In spite of being protected by several constitutional provisions, the overall development of the community is substantially less as compared to the mainstream people of India. Data from the Ministry of Tribal Affairs indicates that while the national child mortality rate is 18.4 per 1000 live births, the same figure for the STs is almost double at 35.8 per 1000 live births. Similarly, the national literacy average in India is 73%, the national literacy average for the STs is at abysmal 59%. While STs constitute 8.6% of the total population, it is estimated that they have constituted 40% of all people who have been displaced from 1951 to 1990, mostly due to the construction of dams, mines, industrial development, and the creation of wildlife parks and sanctuaries.¹⁰ While, only 24.7% of the ST population that was displaced during this period was rehabilitated (Wahi & Bhatia, 2018).

Autonomous District Council (ADC) and Tribal Rights

In the process of making India a democratic structure in the post-British era, and British Raj was rolling back its feet from its decade long colony, it proposed for a governing structure for new India that initiated for an Advisory Committee to consider the Fundamental Rights of Minorities, Tribal Areas, etc.,¹¹ under the leadership of Sardar Patel in the Constituent Assembly of India. Many sub-committees were formed accordingly to report on the status of tribal areas, one among them being A. V. Thakkar and G. P. Bardoloi committee. Bardoloi committee submitted its report with the conclusion that, the tribal should be provided with sufficient level of autonomy at the district level in tribal areas as a token gesture by Indian state in exchange of giving up the demand of independent state. This to a great extent helped India to deal with its integration process. Eventually, ADCs were constituted consisting of 21 articles, expanding through 20 pages in the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution. The provision for ADCs¹² in the constitution sought to preserve the distinct tribal culture, their social organisations and belief systems. It also addressed the lurking insecurity among the tribal population due to constant intrusion of non-tribal population in to their habitation. Additionally, it took up sufficient level of financial autonomy to look after corresponding districts.

Tripura Tribal Areas Autonomous District Council (TTAADC)

After a series of democratic movements initiated by the Indigenous people of Tripura, Tripura Tribal Areas Autonomous District Council (TTAADC) Act 1979 was passed by the Indian parliament and later on constituted on Jan 15th, 1982. TTAADC is vested with Legislative and Executive powers. While the former involves in summoning meetings of the council and approve budget, set forth rules etc., the executive body operates on the decisions. Tripura was further included under Sixth Schedule¹³ in 1985 by the 49th Amendment Act of the Constitution. The primary objective behind setting up the autonomous district council was to empower the Indigenous people to govern themselves and also to bring all round developments of the tribal people and protect and preserve the culture, customs, and traditions of indigenous people. It sought to remove within a short time the material disparities between the advanced and backward sections of the societies; to strengthen the bonds of unity between the tribal and non-tribal masses and to emancipate not only tribal people but all the deprived people from all types of injustice and exploitation.¹⁴ Encompassing 68.10% of the state's total geographical area or 7,132.56 square kms, the ADC set in to operate essentially tribal-compact areas with the aim to introduce internal autonomy and thereby protect the social, economic and cultural interests of the tribal population as a whole. However, as more intrusion of non-tribals took place during 70s, it started setting aside the tribal population, thus threatening their very unique position. Tribal population is therefore struggling for regaining their autonomy in the region.¹⁵

Interfacing Migration and Tribal Population in Tripura

(i) The People of the Land: The people of Tripura represent three distinct ethnic stocks: The Indo-Aryan, the Mon-goloid and the Mundari. The last group i.e., Mundari tribe is a small population that was brought to Tripura to work on tea plantation. The Indo-

Aryan is represented by the im-migrant population which consist of different castes of Hindus and Muslims. The Mon-goloid group represents the indigenous tribal communities. These two major communities constitute almost the entire population of Tripura. The population of Tripura thus could be divided into two primary groups:

- a. *The Tribal (Scheduled Tribes) population*
- b. *The non-Tribal Population.*

The name of the previously princely state Tripura is named after its original inhabitants Tripuras. Having been called Hill Tipperah by the British, the state had been sharing border with Bengal and has always experienced immigration. However, over the last few decades, immigration has assumed an unprecedented scale, resulting in changing the de-mographic composition in the region itself.

Table 1: Major tribes of Tripura state and their population (2001)

Tribes	Population in 2001	Share of a specific tribe in the total tribal population in percent	Areas of concentration
1. Tripuras	543,848	54.74	Scattered all over with maximum concentration in West Tripura
2. Reangs	165,103	16.60	South Tripura and Dhalai
3. Jamatias	74,949	7.54	South Tripura
4. Chakmas	64,293	6.47	North Tripura, Dhalai
5. Halam	47,245	4.75	W. Tripura, Dhalai and N. Tripura
6. Mogh (Mag)	30,385	3.05	South Tripura
7. Mundas and Santals	14,575	1.46	West and North Tripura
8. Garos	11,180	1.12	South Tripura, Dhalai
9. Noatias	6,650	0.67	West Tripura
10. Orang	6,223	0.62	North Tripura
11. Others	28,997	2.90	
Total	993,426	99.92	

Source: Census 2001, A 11 State Primary Census Abstract for individual Scheduled Tribe 2001 Tripura

The Landscape of Migration

Of all the North Eastern States, Tripura has been confronted with the problem of the in-flux of foreign nationals from across the border in a greater magnitude. As the State shares an international boundary with Bangladesh, since the partition of Indian sub-continent (1947), a large number of Bangladeshis have crossed and still continue to cross the border and entered the State. The story of immigration in Tripura is as old as that of Assam, albeit of a different nature. Unlike other Northeast states (like Nagaland, Mizo-ram, Meghalaya, Assam) which did not attract many immigrants due to lack of large tea plantations requiring a labour force and they did not have a fertile alluvial plain to attract peasant immigrants, Tripura and Assam became a hub of immigrants because of a large tea plantation and presence of Brahmapurta and Barak Valleys in these regions that made it fertile and productive.¹⁶ In the wake of partition of India in 1947, the number of immi-grants went high in Assam and Tripura.

Table 2: Immigration in the North East during 1947-1951

District/state	Population 1951	Persons born in other Indian states		Total population born outside the state	Persons born in other countries		Persons born in Pakistan		Persons born outside India		Countries of Europe
		1951	Indian states		Asia (% of total population)	other countries	in Pakistan	(% of people born outside India)	Nepal	Burma	
1. United Khasi-Jaintia Hills	363,599	10,112	36,270 (9.95 %)	26,049 (7.16 %)	16,157 (62 %)	9,496 (36 %)	238	175			
2. Garo Hills	242,075	588	8,926 (3.68 %)	8,335	6,976 (83.7 %)	355 (16.25 %)	—	3			
3. Naga Hills (Nagaland)	205,950	1,392	3,798 (1.8 %)	2,400	1,416 (61 %)	937 (39 %)	30	6			
4. Lushai Hills (Mizoram)	196,202	554	10,360 (5.2 %)	9,786	6,512 (67 %)	1,633 (16.6 %)	1,637 (16.7 %)	20			
5. United Mikir and N. Cachar Hills	165,440	1,652	5,375 (3.2 %)	3,666	3,322 (90.6 %)	323 (8.8 %)	11	7			
6. Mishmi Hills	32,163	2,847	6,178 (19.2 %)	3,331	872 (26.1 %)	2,358 (70.8 %)	51	—			
7. Abor Hills	10,761	837	1,456 (13.5 %)	613	289	289	8	6			
8. Trip Frontiers	5,213	57	1,253 (24.0 %)	645	225	358	33	2			
9. Balipara Frontier	9,721	1,407	2,816 (29 %)	1,408	103	1,300 (92.3 %)	2	1			
10. Manipur	577,635	4,204	6,279 (1.08 %)	2,075	1,394 (67.2 %)	424 (20.4 %)	256	—			
11. Tripura	639,029	18,509	229,089 (35.8 %)	210,568	210,161 (99 %)	270	122	12			
12. Assam	9,043,707	447,414	—	894,607	833,328 (93.15 %)	56,572 (5.06 %)	3,296 (0.4 %)	—			

Source: Census of India (1951, vol. VII, Assam, Manipur and Tripura, pp. 112-135)

More so, unlike other north-east states like Nagaland, Mizoram and Meghalaya where immigration was restricted because of ‘Bengal Regulation of 1873’ also known as ‘inner-line’ restriction,¹⁷ in case of Tripura it was altogether a different case. In absence of inner Line permit, Tripura started receiving an enormous number of immigrants since 20th century. “Bengali refugees from the adjacent districts of East Pakistan poured in. As the population of Hindus increased, more and more Hindus joined the refugee stream, causing an increase in the percentage of immigrant population”.¹⁸ As such the immigration population reached a recorded number in the state constituting up to 36 % of the total population as noticed in 1951.

Table 3: Immigration in Tripura (1891-1951)

Year	Total population of the state	Immigrant population	Percentage of total population
1891	137,442	33,328	24.24
1901	173,325	43,894	25.32
1911	229,613	81,663	35.50
1921	304,437	96,386	31.66
1931	382,450	114,450	29.92
1951	637,029	229,977	36.10

Sources:

Census of India 1891, vol. IV The Lower provinces of Bengal and their Feudatories, Calcutta 1893, p. 389 by C J O’Donnell

Census of India 1901, vol. VI, Lower provinces of Bengal and their Feudatories – Hill Tippera, pt. I, p. 82 by E A Gait

Census of India 1911, vol. V, Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, Sikkim, pt. I, p. 117, Report by L S S O’Malley

Census of India 1921, vol. V Bengal, pt. II, tables, p. 146 by W H Thompson, Calcutta, 1923

Census of India 1931, Bengal and Sikkim, p. 104, by A E Porter, Calcutta, 1933

Census of India (1951:123, 129)

Beginning of Crisis and Impact on Demographic Structure

Continuous influx of foreign nationals in to the state has created a multi-dimensional problem bringing its impact upon all aspects of life and society of the indigenous population of Tripura. Particularly the demographic flow from Bangladesh aroused hostile sentiment in the tribal mind against the Bengali families settled in the hilly areas. The rapid growth of population caused by the large-scale immigration from erstwhile East Pakistan had impacted the inherent ecological, geographical, economical, social, religious, cultural and political aspects of the society (Bhattacharjee, 1989). The census figures indicate that Tripura’s population had shot up from 15,66,341 in 1971 to 20,53,058 persons in 1981. This was an increase of 4, 86, 716 persons within a decade thus swelling of Tripura’s total population. According to a source, an average of 537 Hindus migrated per day from their country to the neighbouring Indian territories during 1971-81. Mercus Fanda, quoting the Government of India sources, states in a newspaper article that by 1981 six lac Bangladeshi nationals came to the north-eastern states of which three lacks in Meghalaya, two lacs in Tripura and one lac in Assam.¹⁹

These figures mentioned above were only the officially registered refugees who were subsequently rehabilitated in different parts of the State. However, influx of illegal Bangladeshis has been a continuous process and the State Authority has not been able to record and register them officially because of the way they entered the State illegally. This had to a great extent, imbalanced and affected the entire demographic structure of the State. The decadal growth rate and density of population in Tripura since 1931 is shown in the following Table.

Table 4: Growth of Tribal and Non-Tribal Population in Tripura

Year	Population	Tribal Population	Non-Tribal Population	Tribal Growth	Non-Tribal Growth
1941	5,13,10	2,56,991	2,56,019	33.68	34.60
1951	6,45,707	2,37,953	4,01,074	(-) 7.40	59.26
1961	11,42,005	3,60,070	7,81,935	51.31	91.76
1971	15,56,342	4,50,544	11,05,798	25.12	41.41
1981	20,53,058	5,83,920	14,69,138	29.60	32.85
1991	27,57,205	8,53,345	19,03,360	46.14	29.56
Source: Census Reports of India 1991					

The table indicates that the growth rate of non-tribal population has been on the higher side as compared to the tribal population in the state. And with this low trend of population growth, the indigenous people seem to reduce into a minority with each passing decade. The Assam Tribune newspaper report of April 9th, 1991, confirms that the continuous influx of foreigners into Tripura would not only upset the demographic profile of the border State but also retard its economic growth. Similar concerns were also expressed by noted author S.R. Bhattacharyya, who articulated in his book, 'Tribal Insurgency in Tripura', that Tripura is the only State in India where the early dwellers (indigenous) have been outnumbered by the inflow of immigrants.²⁰ As such the indigenous people of Tripura, who were in great majority till 1950, were now gradually marginalised and reduced to a minority by the Bengali immigrants.²¹

In the event of continuous influx of immigration and the relative lack of development and representation, the indigenous population began to feel that their rights have been taken away by the immigrants. They began to feel unsecured both economically and politically.

Contentious Grounds for Seeking Autonomy by Indigenous People

The Cultural-Linguistic Rift

Khimji and Maunder observe that the imitation of culture begins at the very beginning of the socialization process. Children acquire the ways of culture such as belief,

behavior, and ways of interaction through participation in schools, where cultural norms and values are transmitted, internalized and rehearsed (Khimji & Maunder, 2012). In most of cases, the culture and norms are being reinforced and reproduced by the ruling class who has exclusive access to the institutions, knowledge system and establishes itself as the basis of knowledge. This Education must not be seen as neutral and separated from class inter-ests (Bourdieu, 1986).²² In a multilingual society, language of the dominant class gets acknowledged as more appropriate medium of communication or instruction than other languages. Apple suggests that there is a nexus between the dominant class and the state and therefore, the language of the dominant group pervades in education (Apple, 1979). This results into some kind of cultural imperialism and is predatory for the vernaculars.

In case of Tripura, there are around 19 major tribal communities and ethnic groups who speak in different languages.²³ These languages include: Bengali, Kokborok, Bongcher, Halam, Mog, Chakma, Kuki, Mizo, Lushai, Garo, Hindi, Santal or Santali, Chaimali, Kudukh, Bhili, Mundari, Meiteilon, etc. However, only Bengali and Kokborok has been used as official languages for communication.²⁴ Moreover, as the non-tribal Bengali population has become prominent in most of political, social and economic domain, the medium of instruction in most of government schools and other institutions has been mostly Bengali or English (Jamatia & Nagaraju, 2019). The first educational institution in Tripura, the *Umakanta*²⁵ was established in Agartala in 1890, founded by Maharaja Bir Chandra Manikya and Bengali was made medium of instruction for the same.

Fig 2: District wise Linguistic and Religious distribution of STs of Tripura

As Bengali language has been given priority in school curriculum across the state, it sought to propagate a sense of homogeneity among the Bengali ethnic community by constructing and popularising historical events and popular icons through various poems and proses. The Bengali textbook for Class VIII depicts about the partition of Bengal (1905) and unity among the Bengalis by connecting narratives of the partition of Bengal (1905) and its language movement (1952) and how Bengalis have integrated and collectively agitated against the partition and imposition of Urdu language in Bangladesh. Furthermore, Tripura's History textbooks ignored the significant contributions of many local kings of Tripura. For instance, both Maharaja Radha Kishore Manikya (1896–1909) and Maharaja Bir Bikram Kishore Manikya Bahadur (1908–1947) were concerned about the introduction of education in the state, and they also established schools, airport, colleges etc. Kings of Tripura also had financed the education of Rabindranath Tagore (the Nobel laureate poet). However, the history text books of Tripura are devoid of such local narratives and rather reflect the conscience of general masses as shaped by mainstream discourses.

All these become a matter of contention for the indigenous tribal groups as they find their histories being distorted and less represented in school curriculum and as such they are demanding for inclusion of their languages in educational system and trying to save their language from dying. On 3 August 2016, the committees of minority languages in Tripura organised a rally as a demand to regularise the minority languages in the state.²⁶

Sl. No.	Class	Subject	Title	Author	Prose/Poetry/Historical Narrative
1	VIII	Bengali	He Came One Day	Bandyopadhyay	Prose
2	VIII	Bengali	Purba-Paschim	Kumar Sengupta	Poem
3	VIII	Bengali	Bharat-Bangladesh	Anil Sarkar	Poem
4	VIII	English	Swami Vivekananda	SCERT	Prose
5	IX	Bengali	Ekush	Anil Sarkar	Poem
6	X	History	Temple Architecture of Tripura: Folk Songs, Dances and Festivals of Tripura	Kalyan Chaudhuri and Swagata Bhattacharya	History

Table 5: Representation of Bengali Identity in School Textbooks (Source: Tripura, G. o. Amader Atita Dingulo for class VIII. Agartala: SCERT, 2016; Tripura, G. o. New Tripura Reader for class VIII. Agartala: SCERT, 2016; Tripura, G. o. Madhyamik Bangla Sahita Sankalan. Agartala: SCERT, 2016; Chaudhuri, K., & Bhattacharya, S. Social Science: History and Political Science Textbook for class X. Kolkata: Oriental Book, 2016.)

Misrepresentation of Tripura's History

The history of Tripura has hardly been acknowledged or discussed in the mainstream Indian Historical narratives or textbooks since the beginning of formal education in India. The same is missing even from the Tripura history books for long. There has been substantial lack of representation of history of Tripura in school textbooks. In the recent years, although Government of Tripura has introduced history of Tripura in school curriculum, yet the language and culture of the dominant groups are still being projected as mainstream knowledge of the state. The history of Tripura has been written in accordance with its relation with the mainland India. For example, the school textbooks seek to look for historical connection between 1857 revolt and its reflection on Tripura; the relations between Tripura kings and British Empire during 1862 to 1923 and from 1923 to 1947 and finally how Tripura merges with the Indian state. However, narratives on indigenous people and contribution of kings do not get much place in the discourse. For instance, the king of Tripura in 1850s, Ishan Chandra Manikya (1849–1862) had been accused of favouring British Raj:

It was at that time that Revolt broke out in different parts of North India. Ishan Chandra instead of participating in any anti-British activities rendered all possible help to the Company's Government to suppress the sporadic incidents of rebellions... thus some of the rebels who took shelter near Agartala ignoring the prohibitive order were captured and handed over to the English at Comilla (Jamatia & Nagaraju, 2019).

Another king, Birendra Kishore Manikya (1883–1923) had allegedly donated a sum of one lakh rupees to British during World War I as 'War Fund' in addition to an annual sum of Rupees Fifteen thousand till the war continued. Consequently, he was conferred with the title of Maharaja as a return of favour by Britishers (Jamatia & Nagaraju, 2019). So much so that the reading text portrays some kings—as anti-national and disloyal to the Indian National Movement and make them responsible for continuation of British Raj in India in general and in Tripura in particular. However, contrary to the mainstream narrative, the oral history of Tripura holds that kings of Tripura to a large extent resisted the expansion of British imperialism by stopping recitation and preaching of the Bible in the state and also forbade the British to enter into the state by putting a check on conversion to Christianity and conquering their territory or kingdom.

The spread of Hindu Nationalism through Educational institutions

Tripura, being a multi-religious state, seeks to promote secularism through the school curriculum. In one of its school texts, *Prasna* (Question)—a poem written by Rabindranath Tagore in Bengali textbook for Class VIII, seeks to balance the symbolic gesture of different religious leaders, such as Swami Vivekananda, Sri Chaitanya, Mother Teresa, Jesus Christ, and Lord Buddha. Another text, *Parable of the Talents*—a poem taken from the Gospel of Mathew 25:14–30²⁷ also reflect upon the secular spirit. Nevertheless, there is supremacy of Hindu religious identity and its ideology

that underpins all literature across school curriculum. For instance, prominent literature contains stories of Lava Kuser Jagasa Bandhan—which depicts the Trilok (three worlds) of Ramachandra such as heaven, earth, and hell; Annapurna O Ishwari Patni—portraying the conversation between Annapurna (the other form of Parvati).²⁸ Furthermore, majority of schools in Tripura seem to reinforce Hindu religion by celebrating Saraswati Puja.²⁹ Students usually participate in conducting and organising the essentials of worshipping the deity. There is a tacit inclination towards Hindu ideology that is being sought to be reinforced through medium of communication, texts and festivals. Thus, Sundar questions how far the government schools are really secular is subject to debate? (Sundar, 2004).

Table 6: Representation of religious identity in Poems and Proses in Tripura School Text books

Sl. No.	Class	Title	Religion	Prose/Poem
1	VIII	Swami Vivekananda	Hinduism, Christianity, Buddhism, Islam	Prose
2	VIII	The Sacred River	Tribal Religion	Prose
3	VIII	Swadesh	Hinduism	Prose
4	VIII	Vijaya Dashami	Hinduism	Poem
5	IX	Lava Kuser Jagasa Bandhan	Hinduism	Poem
6	IX	Adivasi Tripura Samajer Puja Utsav	Tribal Religion and Hinduism	Poem
7	IX	Boro Devta Ebong Machang	Tribal Religion	Short Prose
8	X	O Dumbur	Hinduism	Prose
9	X	Annapurna O Ishwari Patni	Hinduism	Poem

Source: Tripura, G. o. Amader Atita Dingulo for class VIII. Agartala: SCERT, 2016; Tripura, G. o. New Tripura Reader for class VIII. Agartala: SCERT, 2016; Tripura, G. o. Madhyamik Bangla Sahita Sankalan. Agartala: SCERT, 2016.

Development Crisis: Land and Agriculture

Tribal people in Tripura traditionally depended on shifting cultivation -- locally known as jhum. Under this system, a small patch of land is being cleared in the forest and used for cultivation and another patch of land is burnt and prepared for agriculture in

the following year. And this process continued. In this process, previously used lands are not utilised again thus allowing regeneration of the forest in the area. However, with more and more people becoming dependent on agriculture, cultivation was carried out on the same land every season leading to jhum-cultivating affecting the forests. Further, as "In 1982, the government declared that all open protected forests would be treated as un-classed government forests,"³⁰ it led to massive displacement of tribal population as they could not continue jhum cultivation in the protected forests anymore and were forced to shift to the reserve forests. Since there were restrictions on Jhum, the indigenous people had no option but to move to nearby state for cultivation or depend upon the public distribution system (PDS) for food consumption. This destroyed the self-sustained economy of the tribal villages in the hill-tracts".³¹

Contemporary Debate an Citizenship Amendment Act 2019 and its implications

Although immigration to the state has been a perennial issue, the immigrants were welcomed initially as they form the persecuted community in the host state. However, with the swelling of Tripura's population due to ongoing immigrants most of the resources, job opportunities are being occupied not by Muslim Bengalis but by Hindu Bengalis and they also become part of the administration. Hobo, a tribal student expresses, "we are no longer safe in our homeland because of illegal migrants. We are losing jobs and resources to the Bangladeshis."³² Even in the administrative position most of the MLAs, bureaucrats, ministers and people holding constitutional posts are from Bangladesh. Unlike other north east states like Mizoram, Meghalaya, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, where the local indigenous people usually control the decision making process, in Tripura, the indigenous people remain toothless when it comes to sharing power structure in the administration.

With the Citizenship Amendment Act, 2019 being enacted recently, it resurfaces the existing tensions and tribal angst in the region with widespread protest across North-East including Tripura. Many communal clashes have erupted in the heart of the region. "More than 1500 non-tribal residents left their homes in Kanchanpur due to alleged attacks by Bru community in support of the anti-CAB movement. "They took out violent procession against CAB and raised communal slogans against the non-tribals. They attacked and tortured whoever they found on their way, in the roads, markets, shops, and houses, destroyed properties, which created tension in the locality and forced the families to take shelter in the makeshift camps" said Khirud Nath, a BOM activist.³³ Protesters in Northeast, particularly in Tripura argue that the move would lead to the dilution of Tribal identity as CAA would allow all the Non-Muslim Bangladeshi immigrants to take up Indian citizenship and they would now be able to settle in the region legally.³⁴ Citing the situation of the Tribes getting worse, the Indigenous people have united to oppose this Act as they felt their motherland is being taken away from them and their existence is under jeopardy. Although the government has assured to make exceptions for the north east, yet it has failed to assuage pertinent issues. "There is one ADC in the state and it covers about 70 per cent of the area. But Tripura is on the boil because two-thirds of the state's population stays in the 30 per cent of the region where CAB would apply".³⁵ Recently, the Tripura Tribal Areas

Autonomous District Council (TTAAD) along with In-digenous People's Front of Tripura (IPFT) initiated a roadblock strike demanding for a separate state to be carved out of Tripura, a demand which has been going on for long time.³⁶ As such the CAA is seen as a direct threat on the indigenous tribal community in the region and it may give rise to insurgency and fear psychosis in the state. "While al-most all militant outfits are now neutralised, tribals fear that the citizenship law will fur-ther weaken their grip on the state by opening arms to Bengali migrants".³⁷

The Indigenous People Front of India (IPFT) who aligned with Bhartiya Janta Party (BJP) to form government in Tripura has time and again voiced out their demand for 'Tipland' — a separate state for tribal people. While promises of considering the de-mands for a separate state were given by the current BJP government before forming the government, however, it has altered such promises and is settling down the issue with 'creating a modality committee' to look after the overall development of Tribals in the state. Meanwhile, IPFT submitted a memorandum to the Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of India for the perusal of the High Powered Committee formed saying ".....while making recommendation to make the suitable steps for addressing the issues related to social, economic, educational, linguistic, cultural etc. problems of the tribal of the state, the High Level Committee should make serious attempts to find out the reasons behind the demand for the separate state of 'Tipland' and address the related issues accordingly" (Deb, 2018). Besides this, Mr. Bijoy Kumar Hrangkhawl, President of Indigenous Nationalist Party of Tripura (INPT) led a Five-member delegation to the committee members and kept a demand for Inner Line Permit and operation of NRC in Tripura to secure and protect the local interests of tribal population.

Present-day Instability and Precarious Lives

While the Citizenship Amendment Act has been widely criticized for breaking the con-stitution's secular ideals and discriminating against the Muslim population, tensions in the Northeast, notably Tripura, have risen for a variety of reasons. The continuous migration driven by partition and subsequent religious discord in former East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) has resulted in a massive influx of Bengalis since the 1950s, and the corresponding exclusion of indigenous people from administrative, eco-nomic, and political structures, as well as a diminishing status in linguistic, educational, and cultural domains, has long distraught the indigenous tribal communities in the state, and the potential implementation of CAA has only fueled this up. "Non-tribals owned or controlled 90% of land that did not belong to the government, according to a media in-quiry in the late 1970s. Some of the Manikyas' land deeded to Tripuri communities was used to settle refugees, while others were encroached upon." The enclaves of indigenous peoples remain the least developed in the region. The state's current proposal for devel-opment with natural gas reserves and trading with Bangladesh has enraged the tribal community because it mostly benefits the state's Bengali majority. Local ethnic groups such as the Borok, Reang, Noatia, and Halam, among others, have been fighting the im-plementation of CAA in particular, because the new law allows undocumented non-Muslim migrants from Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Bangladesh to become citizens of India. The fear of losing one's original identity, as well as the resulting overcrowding of land and resources as a result of a potential inflow of refugees,

has sparked widespread protests across Tripura's districts. Moreso, the violation to the instrument of accession that India had signed with Tripura on 15th October 1949 by Rajmata Kanchan Prabha Devi, also caused resentment amongst the native Tribal community.

Demanding to keep Tripura out of CAA and not to treat Tripura like a dumping ground for illegal migrants. Many tribal associations, including tribal political parties such as the National Council of Tripura (NCT), Indigenous Nationalist Party of Tripura (INPT), Tipraland State Party (TSP), and several other social organisations such as the Borok People Human Rights Organisation (BPHRO), came out to protest against CAA. At least 15000 people attended a big protest march held in various sections of the state. "We are not against the Bengali community or any religious community," said Animesh Debbarma, Chairman of the National Conference of Tripura (NCT), "but we want to protect and safeguard the rights of our people." We want the act repealed or the entire state of Tripura exempted from its provisions." Such demands for the restoration of tribal lands were first made in 1978 by the Tripura National Volunteers (TNV), and then again in 1979 by the Left-led government, which moved the Tripura Autonomous District Council Bill to the assembly in an attempt to restore tribal lands taken by non-tribals, but it resulted in widespread violence in the region, killing around 1800 people. Although both tribals and Bengali groups have worked to maintain peace in the region over the years, each have acquired fears and phobias about their own survival, leading to aspirations for separate 'Tipraland' and 'Banglasthan'.

The betrayal of the tribal community over 70 years after repeated assurances from governments to maintain their land, culture, ethnicity, and political identity has made them increasingly upset and troubled, and they see implementation as a step that could lead to the tribe's extinction. While the leading political party BJP and Indigenous Peoples Front of Tripura (IPFT) won the election in early 2018 on the lines of restoring and protecting the tribal community, however, IPFT distanced itself from BJP over the aspects of CAA and NRC. IPFT vigorously opposed the CAA's implementation and called for Tipraland, a separate state for tribals in Tripura, as a solution to protect the state's indigenous people. In a similar vein, TIPRA Motha, which has emerged as Tripura's single-largest tribal political party and won the Tripura Tribal Areas Autonomous District Council (TTAADC) alongside its ally Indigenous Nationalist Party of Twipra (INPT), has been outspoken about the importance of tribal communities' identity and integrity. TIPRA Motha, led by Pradyot Kishore Debbarma, has been renamed The Indigenous People's Regional Alliance as a new political party (TIPRA). The party's desire for a Greater Tipraland has been a key step forward in the region's construction of new statehood. The new demand aims to bring under the Tripura Tribal Areas Autonomous District Council (TTAADC) every tribal person living in indigenous areas or villages, as well as the Tripuri tribals in Tripura, Assam, Mizoram, and parts of Bangladesh. Under Pradyot Kishore Debbarma's leadership, the party has called for an NRC and filed a court petition to bring justice to the land and its people. Similarly, the state's existing Bengali community has been vocal in its opposition to the NRC's implementation. The Bengali population, haunted by memories of war, partition, relocation, and violence, has also requested a separate region for

Bengalis, as well as assurances that no Bengali in Tripura will be disenfranchised or uprooted as a result of the NRC. NRC continues to be painful for many residents, particularly the Hindu Bengali population, because many of them may be labelled as illegal citizens under the NRC if they fail to show documents and face deportation. Tripura People's Party (TRP), a local political party created in 2015, reiterated the concerns, calling for the cancellation of both the CAA and the statewide NRC revision, as well as an exemption for its implementation in Tripura. There is widespread perception that the new law will further split people along ethnic and sectarian lines, triggering bloodshed that Tripura thought it had put behind decades ago.

Conclusion

The state is currently hamstrung by resurfacing of communal politics and regional instability. Reflecting upon the consequences of CAA, Indigenous Progressive Regional Alliance (TIPRA) states that the illegal immigrants, who if become legal after Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) being implemented, will not be allowed to stay in the state: "Our state has accommodated a large number of migrants from the then East Pakistan after the partition of the country and has no space to accommodate any more." The state of Tripura has already been witnessing hatred sentiments amongst its people and seeds of communalism and sporadic violence has started to rise in the state. Around 20th October 2021, a series of riots took place in many parts of Tripura in which shops and mosques were vandalized and burnt by the mob. Most of these shops were considerably belonged to the minority Muslims in Chamtila, Rowa villages. The attacks were considerably triggered after a huge rally led by Vishva Hindu Parishad (VHP) and other local religious groups in Panisagar protested against the attacks on Hindus in neighbouring Bangladesh and soon many parts in the region erupted with violence. The instability and precarious of lives continue to haunt the state for a while now. As such taking quick moves to implement the CAA may not be the most successful tactic for the government right now, instead, what is needed is for the government to restore peace and acquire the trust and confidence of the people in the state now. Implementing CAA may also be a factor in changing the power dynamics in the region. The continuous resistance against CAA by both tribals and non-tribals in the state along with gaining popularity of TIPRA Motha and other tribal associations and groups may weaken the legitimacy that the BJP leadership is enjoying present. The emergence of new regional political groups may also strengthen the existing demands for creating a Greater Tripaland for further integration of tribal communities in the state and beyond which may lead to breaking the state into parts and formation of new identities may arise up in near future.

Notes

1 <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/trouble-in-tripura-19707> accessed on 18th Aug, 2019

2 Ibid.

3 JMCAB is an umbrella organisation of tribal parties and indigenous social organisations, which was floated to oppose the CAB. Indigenous Nationalist Party of

Tripura (INPT), National Conference of Tripura (NCT) and Tipraland State Party (TSP) have come together to form this new platform. JMCAB has demanded Tripura's complete exemption from the ambit of the CAB.

4 In his book "The Aborigines-So-called-and Their Future" (1943), Ghurye refuted the pre-existing belief that tribal communities occupied their respective territory prior to the settlement of non-tribal or they lived in isolation aloof from them and therefore insisted on the "objective" value of the social institutions in competition with one another. Unlike Ghurye, Elwin believed that institutional competition with that of Tribes is bound to destroy the wisdom of tribal institutions which they have gathered over centuries.

5 Article 366 (25) of the Constitution of India refers to Scheduled Tribes as those communities, who are scheduled in accordance with Article 342 of the Constitution. It says that only those communities who have been declared as such by the President Through an initial public notification or through a subsequent amending Act of Parliament will be considered to be Scheduled Tribes. The list of Scheduled Tribes is State/UT specific and a community declared as a Scheduled Tribe in a State need not be so in another State. The inclusion of a community as a Scheduled Tribe is an ongoing process. The essential characteristic, first laid down by the Lokur Committee, for a community to be identified as Scheduled Tribes are:- a) Indications of primitive traits; b) Distinctive culture; c) Shyness of contact with the community at large; d) Geographical isolation; and e) Backwardness

6 For more refer to <https://tribal.nic.in/ST/Statistics8518.pdf>

7 Census 2011 Report

8 Available at URL: http://factsanddetails.com/india/Minorities_Castes_and_Regions_in_India/sub7_4h/entry-4216.html

9 "Tribal belt" embraces central and northeast India, which extends across the center of India from Pakistan in the west to Bangladesh and Myanmar in the east. The belt is home to 81 million indigenous people, whose ancestors may have inhabited India before Aryan invaders, the ancestors of Hindus, arrived around 1500 B.C.

10 During 1951-1990, 85 lakh tribal folk were displaced due to dams, mines, industries, wildlife sanctuaries, etc., which is 40% of total displacement. Please see Annual Report of the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, 2016-2017. Also available at URL: https://tribal.nic.in/writereaddata/Annual_Report/AnnualReport2016-17.pdf, pp. 47

11 On May 16th, 1946 British Prime Minister Atlee set forth a mandate of creating effective governing institutions

12 While normal Indian districts are carved out due to administrative efficiency, the ADCs have been created specially to give representation to particular tribal ethnic communities in the North-East. These ADCs with respect to power sharing locate themselves somewhere above the local governments and below state governments and are mandated to integrate tribal populations as communities within the Indian state.

13 The Sixth Schedule to the Constitution of India provides exclusive powers to the district council for self-Governance of the tribal population of the state. The district council has its own powers to appoint its own staff in terms of requirement and appointment rules.

14 Please see URL: https://archive.india.gov.in/knowindia/state_uts.php?id=101 15 Ibid. 13 16 Dikshit, K.R. and Jutta K.Dikshit (2014), *Advances in Asian Human Environmental Research, North East India: Land, People and Economy*, Springer Publications. 17 It stipulated that plainsman could not cross the borders of these well defined scheduled areas without proper permission.

18 Cited in Sibopada De (2005), *Illegal Migrations and the North East: A study of Migrants from Bangladesh*, Anamika Publishers and Distributors

19 Cited in Sibopada De (2005), *Illegal Migrations and the North East: A study of Migrants from Bangladesh*, Anamika Publishers and Distributors

20 Ganguly, J.B., "Tripura: Influx of Foreigners to Retard Economic Growth", *The Assam Tribune*, (Guwahati), April 9, 1991, p. 3.

21 Ahmed, Syed Zubair, "Outsiders' Helpness in N.E. Ethnic Tension", *The Sunday Times of India*, (New Delhi), June 5, 1994, p. 9.

22 Pierre Bourdieu in "The Forms of Capital."

23 Like Tripuri, Reang, Jamatia, Chakma, Halam, Mog, Munda, Noatia, Garo, Oraon, Kuki, Bhil, Santal, Uchoi, Chaimal, Khasi, Lepcha and Bhutia. Please see Tribal Research and Cultural Institute, "Different Tribes of Tripura" 2018.

24 As per the 2011 census report, about 23.97 % speak Kokborok language in Tripura, see kokborokml.tripura.gov.in

25 Gradually it was further developed and in 1904, renamed as Umakanta Academy, in recognition of contributions of Sri Umakanta Das to the institution.

26 Chakma National Council of India and Tripura Chakma Association, Bishnupriya Manipuri Development Samiti, Tripura Manipuri Students Existing Youth Committee and Tripura Manipuri Development Committee are the organizations who march to institutionalize the minority languages in Tripura.

27 It is considered as one of the parables of Jesus Christ, where he is preaching his disciples.

28 Annapurna is represented as Devi/Ma, a Hindu married woman prohibited to call her husband by name, she is wife of Shiva, a Hindu God. We also find devotees worshipping her at Kashi (in Uttar Pradesh) every year in the month of Chaitra (March-April) during Sukla-Ashtami Tithi.

29 Saraswati, a Hindu goddess of knowledge who is worshipped every year on Vasant Panchmi (5th day of Spring according to Hindu calendar)

30 Cited by P N Ray, principal chief conservator of forests, Tripura in an interview in 2015. Available at <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/trouble-in-tripura-19707> accessed on 18th Aug, 2019

31 Cited by Dipak Dutta Ray, chief conservator of forests, Tripura. Available at Available at <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/cab-protests-in-northeast-tripura-remains-tense-but-peaceful-1627495-2019-12-11>

32 Ibid

33 Please see <http://www.uniindia.com/anti-cab-agitation-in-tripura-tension-continues-in-kanchanpur-and-gandacherra/east/news/1821322.html> 34 Available at <https://www.dailyo.in/variety/citizenship-amendment-bill-cab-tripura-northeast-nellie-massacre/story/1/32279.html>

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Available at <https://www.dnaindia.com/india/report-inpt-blocks-nh-and-railway-tracks-demanding-separate-state-2497210> accessed on 23rd Aug, 2019

³⁷ Available at <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/people-vs-citizenship-assam-northeast-bjp-6167388/>

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